

**Diderot and the Ideal of Paternalistic Monarchy. An Enlightenment Struggle
against Moral Decay and for Political Harmony**

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Abstract

Since the 1990s, there has been a growing tendency to interpret Diderot as a radical who first put into question absolutism in the *Encyclopédie* and then became a fierce opponent of any kind of “despotism”, even the “enlightened” one, and a fervent partisan of democratic revolutions in the 1770s. It is argued here that the narrative that cuts Diderot’s life into different phases obscures continuities in his political thought, and misrepresents partly the political vision he had in the 1770s. Diderot’s political thought may have been more coherent than usually acknowledged, and this coherence is to be found in his ideal of a paternalistic monarchy taking advice from its subjects and respecting their rights, that is the constitution of the realm. This idea is not to be mixed up with a democratic programme of government by the people, nor with the endorsement of political change via a revolution. Rather, when towards the end of his life Diderot lost hope that the constitutional order of the French monarchy would be respected, he both *feared* civil war and hoped that these tumults might bring about the regeneration of the French monarchy. This vision derived from a classical cyclic view of history.

Keywords:

Enlightenment; Political Thought; Denis Diderot; Monarchy; Revolution

“Ce plan [de prise en charge des malades] n’est pas impraticable; il ne sera pas même dispendieux quand de meilleures loix, quand une administration plus vigilante, plus éclairée et sur-tout plus humaine présidera a ces établissemens. L’essai s’en fait aujourd’hui avec succès sous nos yeux par les soins de Madame Necker. Tandis que son mari travaille plus en grand à diminuer le nombre des malheureux, elle s’occupe des détails qui peuvent

soulager ceux qui existent. [...] Etrangers, devenus membres de la nation par la plus méritoire de toutes les naturalisations, par le bien que vous lui faites, couple généreux, j'ose vous nommer, quoique vivants, quoique environnés du crédit d'une grande place ; et je ne crains pas qu'on m'accuse d'adulation. Je crois avoir assez prouvé que je ne savais ni craindre ni flatter le vice puissant ; et j'ai acquis par là le droit de rendre hautement
hommage à la vertu.”

Denis Diderot, in: Raynal, *Histoire des deux Indes* (Geneva: Jean-Léonard Pellet, 1780)1780, t. 3, 265

“L’histoire ancienne qui nous entretient sans cesse de grands personnages, attache si rarement nos regards sur la multitude, que nous ne l’imaginons pas dans les temps passés aussi grossière, aussi perverse que de nos jours ; peu s’en faut que nous ne croyions qu’on ne traversait pas une rue d’Athènes, sans être coudoyé par un Démosthène ou par un Cimon. Et l’avenir pourrait bien croire, à moins que l’esprit philosophique ne s’introduise à la fin dans l’histoire, qu’on ne traversait pas une rue de Paris, sans coudoyer un N[ecker], un M[alesherbes], ou un T[urgot].”

Denis Diderot, *Essai sur les règnes de Claude et de Néron, et sur les mœurs et les écrits de Sénèque*, 2 vols. (Londres: s. n., 1782), vol. 2, paragraphe 78, 160.

For an Enlightenment *philosophe*, praising powerful courtiers could be detrimental to one’s reputation. Denis Diderot, lauding highly some French ministers who had been, or were still in power at the time the texts quoted above were printed, clearly feared being considered a sycophant, and insisted that his warm compliments stemmed from sincere admiration. Should we believe him? How shall we interpret his endorsement of some of the most influential French politician’s political action? Was this the expression of a sincere admiration or was Diderot rather flattering powerful courtiers to obtain some advantages?

Answering these questions means examining Diderot’s political thought, which has been subject to many scholarly debates since the 1960s. While in many older publications Diderot was deemed to be more conservative and less proto-revolutionary than Rousseau, since the 1990s, there has been a growing tendency to interpret him as a radical who first put into question absolutism in the *Encyclopédie* and then became a fierce opponent of any kind of “despotism”, even the “enlightened” one, and a fervent partisan of democratic revolutions in the 1770s. This interpretation, whose most refined version might have been developed by

Gianluigi Goggi, has largely found its way into biographies, and of course also into Jonathan Israel's famous trilogy. Furthermore, biographers usually see a coherence between Diderot's ideas and his actions: He is supposed to have rejected and kept distance from princely courts, and even while at Catherine's court in Saint-Petersburg to have been quite the contrary of a courtier.¹ To be sure, this new standard interpretation of Diderot's life has not hindered scholars to explore influences on Diderot's thought that do not fit neatly into the narrative of a *philosophe* in opposition to absolute monarchy and – at least in the last phase of his life – in favour of democratic revolutions. Yong-Mock Lee has revealed the strong influence of Jansenist *parlementaires* (that is judges of the Paris Parlement, the highest judicial court of the kingdom) on Diderot's articles for the *Encyclopédie*, and Goggi has not neglected to study the impact of physiocracy on Diderot in the 1760s. It also appears clearly from these studies that Diderot was not a systematic thinker and that he sometimes mobilised heterogeneous ideas. Yet there seems to be a wide scholarly consensus on the fact that “le dernier Diderot” (that is Diderot from about 1770 to his death in 1784) did experience a kind of conversion to ideas announcing the French Revolution. Goggi speaks of a “revolutionary choice” or “bet”, and claims that Diderot was beneath Mably the *philosophe* who developed most clearly a revolutionary scenario.²

If we think of the “latter Diderot” as a proto-revolutionary, the almost panegyric praise he professed for French ministers is surprising, or indeed disturbing. Turgot or Necker, whom

¹ Paolo Quintili, “Le stoïcisme révolutionnaire de Diderot dans l’*Essai sur Sénèque* par rapport à la contribution à l’*Histoire des deux Indes*,” *Recherches sur Diderot et sur l’Encyclopédie* 36 (2004): 29–42; Gianluigi Goggi, *De l’Encyclopédie à l’éloquence républicaine. Étude sur Diderot et autour de Diderot* (Paris: Honoré Champion, 2013); see the articles in Isabelle Deflers (ed.), *Diderot und die Macht / Diderot et le pouvoir* (Berlin: Erich Schmidt Verlag, 2015), and especially Michel Kerautret, “Diderot et la Révolution américaine,” in Deflers (ed.), *Diderot und die Macht*, 101–19; Jonathan Israel, *Democratic Enlightenment: philosophy, revolution, and human rights, 1750–1790* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2012), for example p. 619–626. Biographies: Gerhardt Stenger, *Diderot. Le combattant de la liberté* (Paris: Perrin, 2013); Johanna Borek, *Denis Diderot* (Reinbek: Rowohlt, 2000); Raymond Trousson, *Diderot* (Paris: Éd. Opéra, 2007); P. N. Furbank, *Diderot. A critical biography* (London: Secker & Warburg, 1992); Andrew S. Curran, *Diderot and the Art of Thinking Freely* (New York: Other Press, 2019), 348–367. The most nuanced biography may be Arthur M. Wilson, *Diderot* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1957).

² Yong-Mock Lee, “Diderot et la lutte parlementaire au temps de l’*Encyclopédie*,” *Recherches sur Diderot et sur l’Encyclopédie* 29 (2000), 45–63 (1st part) and 30 (2001), 93–126 (2nd part); Goggi, *De l’Encyclopédie*, 346–536.

Diderot claimed to admire greatly, were certainly reform-oriented ministers, but they never put absolute monarchy into question or worked towards a democratization of the political system. One might thus be tempted to conclude that Diderot was insincere and merely fawning over powerful men.

Such an interpretation may be erroneous, however, as this article intends to show. While, of course, by praising influential politicians, Diderot was acting as a faithful client, he was also consistent with the political vision he had had for decades. It is argued here that the narrative that cuts Diderot's life into different, neatly differentiated phases, obscures some continuities in his political thought, and misrepresents partly the political vision he had towards the end of his life, in the 1770s. This article claims that Diderot's political thought may have been more coherent than usually acknowledged, and that this coherence is to be found in his ideal of a monarchy taking advice from its subjects and respecting their rights, that is the constitution of the realm. This idea is not to be mixed up with a democratic programme of government by the people, nor with the project of realising a change of political system via a revolution. Rather, when towards the end of his life Diderot lost hope that the constitutional order of the French monarchy would be respected, he both *feared* civil war and hoped that these tumults, which were inevitable in his eyes, might bring about, after a long period of pain and bloodshed, the regeneration of the French monarchy. This vision was not an endorsement of revolution as a mean to create a modern and just political system, but rather derived from a classical cyclic view of history.

This interpretation puts the dichotomy between a Radical and a Moderate Enlightenment into question, and brings Diderot closer to the mainstream of Enlightenment political thought. To estimate political radicalism viz. moderation among Enlightenment philosophes, one can take two criteria: firstly, the extent to which the philosophe's ideas put into question the political order of the society in which he lived; secondly, the extent to which he articulated these ideas in the public sphere, or even developed a political action to realise them. This article maintains

that Diderot was not a radical philosopher according to either of these criteria. But it does not only endeavour to criticise merely the slightly anachronistic interpretation of Diderot as an intellectual father of democratic revolution; the aim is rather to understand Diderot's political thought on its own terms, as resulting from a consistent and realistic political project.

This essay focusses on three moments of Diderot's philosophical career – his article “Autorité politique” in the *Encyclopédie* (published in 1751), his acting in favour of physiocracy in the 1760s and his public positions and silences in the 1770s – and tries to show that there were some important continuities between these three periods. The main focus is on the history of ideas, but it is also claimed here that Diderot's public stances, and in some cases his avoidance of public political positioning, must be interpreted in the context of patronage relationships, and that thus Diderot's writings were not disconnected from the world of princely courts, even if he often judged courts and courtiers very harshly. Often enough, Diderot's public positions may have diverged from his private thoughts. This was not only due to the fact that his imprisonment in Vincennes had taught him prudence; Diderot may have been pragmatic because his desire for social promotion for himself and his family set clear limits to what he was ready to claim in public as well as how he orientated his statements. But Diderot's participation in politics was probably not merely a cynic act. He seems to have endorsed the reform programme of his patrons and worked for a betterment of French absolute monarchy.

To be sure, Diderot was not a moderate philosophe in religious issues, even if his public statements in this matter also strongly differed from his convictions, for example when he in his *Essai sur Sénèque* he reproached Rousseau with having questioned Christian dogma.³ In some contexts (especially in letters and manuscript writings), he has also expressed unconventional ideas pertaining to sexual morality. Neither was he a moderate in the sense of presenting himself as a moderate, at least in the last period of his life. He did not call on

³ Denis Diderot, *Essai sur les règnes de Claude et de Néron, et sur les mœurs et les écrits de Sénèque*, 2 vols. (Londres: s. n., 1782), vol. 1, 99-100.

moderation, or criticise radicalism. On the contrary, he often stylised himself as an unconventional writer formulating daring thoughts. When Friedrich-Melchior Grimm criticised Abbé Raynal for presenting himself as the author of the forbidden multi-volumed book *The History of the Two Indies*, Diderot famously penned in a letter an impassioned answer in which he claimed that the *philosophe* has to stand for truth with his own name, even if this truth and this public commitment cause a scandal.⁴ Yet we should not follow Diderot's self-presentation uncritically. That this letter was never sent, and perhaps never intended to be sent, should already call for more caution. Just as an appeal to moderation can help to make a radical argument socially acceptable, the self-staging as a radical can possibly help to conceal an integration into certain powerful circles and political interests. The fact that Diderot reacted so sensitively to Charles Palissot's satire, that presented him as a hypocrite self-staging himself as an independent philosopher but in fact serving aristocrats and princes, and later feared Rousseau's critique, might be a clue that there was a shred of truth in that accusation.⁵ I have indeed shown elsewhere that Diderot was a client not only of Catherine II, but also of several ministers and aristocrats, and that this social and political context may have had an impact on his writings that is largely underestimated or even unexplored in scholarship.⁶ In the following article, I will thus try to situate briefly Diderot's statements on the right political system in their immediate social and political context.

This article is part of a broader reconsideration of Enlightenment history initiated some years ago in a monograph with Andreas Pečar and pursued in a series of articles – some of them

⁴ Denis Diderot, *Correspondance*, eds. Georges Roth and Jean Varloot (Paris: Les Editions de Minuit, 1970), vol. 15, 213–4. This letter does not appear in all editions of the correspondence because, as we shall see, its status is problematic.

⁵ See Diderot's reaction to Palissot's play *Le Satirique* in 1770: Letter to Sartine, June 1770, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 1017–1019.

⁶ Andreas Pečar / Damien Tricoire, "Diderot the Courtier? Philosophers and the World of the Court in Enlightenment Europe," in Thomas Biskup / Benjamin Marschke / Andreas Pečar / Damien Tricoire *Enlightenment at Court, Patrons, Philosophes and Reformers in Eighteenth-Century Europe* (Liverpool: Liverpool University Press, 2022 (= *Oxford University Studies in the Enlightenment*), 33–68.

on Diderot – and in a forthcoming monograph on the Enlightenment.⁷ One result of these investigations is that Enlightenment studies present anachronisms stemming from the fact that scholarship is mainly searching for the intellectual roots of modernity in the eighteenth century. Instead, it may be more useful to contextualise more closely Enlightenment texts – a programme that is not original in any sense and that should be rather consensual among historians, but that it regularly disregarded in practice. Putting Diderot’s political comments and statements into their close context helps to prevent them being interpreted in the light of the French Revolution, or indeed of modern liberal democracy. This article claims for example that there is a danger in over-estimating the scope of Diderot’s criticism of Russian despotism, or of his defence of the American Revolution, just as there are in scholarship frequent over-interpretations of his statements on colonial policy.⁸

The good absolute monarchy in the *Encyclopédie* (early 1750s)

Diderot never penned any substantial work in political theory and he was not in any sense a systematic thinker. The writing that comes closest to a political theory is his famous article “Autorité politique”, published in 1751 in the first volume of the *Encyclopédie*. This article has been interpreted in scholarship in widely different manners: whereas a minority of scholars, above all Jacques Proust, see it as an absolutist piece, many more suggest that it is a strong attack on absolute monarchy with a revolutionary potential.⁹ That many recent publications

⁷ See above all Andreas Pečar / Damien Tricoire, *Falsche Freunde. War die Aufklärung wirklich die Geburtsstunde der Moderne?* Frankfurt am Main (Campus) 2015; Damien Tricoire, “Raynal’s and Diderot’s Patriotic History of the two Indies, or The Problem of Anticolonialism in the Eighteenth Century”, *The Eighteenth Century: Theory and Interpretation* 59/4 (2018), 429–448; idem, “The Fabrication of the *philosophe*: Catholicisms, Court Culture and the Origins of the Enlightenment Moralism”, *Journal for Eighteenth-Century Studies* 51/4 (2018), 453–477; idem, “Súarez liest Diderot oder Von der Recht-und-Ordnung-Ideologie der *Encyclopédie*”, in Andreas Heyer (ed.), *Der lange Weg zur Revolution. Das politische Denken Denis Diderots* (Baden-Baden: Nomos, 2021), 123–140; Andreas Pečar / Damien Tricoire, “Diderot the Courtier? Philosophers and the World of the Court in Enlightenment Europe,” in Thomas Biskup, Benjamin Marschke, Andreas Pečar and Damien Tricoire (eds.), *Enlightenment at Court. Patrons, philosophes and reformers in eighteenth-century Europe* (Liverpool: Liverpool University Press, forthcoming in 2022 in the series *Oxford University Studies in the Enlightenment*), 33–68.

⁸ Tricoire, “Raynal’s and Diderot’s Patriotic History.”

⁹ Diderot against absolutism: John Lough, *Essays on the Encyclopédie of Diderot and d’Alembert* (London: Oxford University Press, 1968), 424–462; idem, *Encyclopédie* (London: Longman, 1971), 285–293; Arthur M. Wilson, *Diderot* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1972), 142; Pierre Chartier, “Fondements anthropologiques de la

tend to follow this latter interpretation is all the more surprising when one takes into consideration that Yong-Mock Lee has already in 2000 presented an alternative to both these views. Lee shows convincingly that “Autorité politique”, and some other of Diderot’s contributions to the *Encyclopédie*, were influenced by theories of *parlementaires*.¹⁰ Yet this argument also raises some questions, as it is clear that Diderot was not strongly interested in supporting the Parlement’s struggles, especially when it came to the quarrels over the Papal bull Unigenitus or the “billets de confessions”. The very fact that the proximity between Diderot’s theories and those of Jansenist *parlementaires* was only discovered through Lee’s meticulous investigation of possible sources suggests that Diderot did not participate directly in *parlementaire* battles, but rather appropriated constitutional theories in a slightly different context.

In the middle of the eighteenth century, preparing the publication of the first volume of the *Encyclopédie*, Diderot’s personal situation and the networks in which he acted made it rather improbable that he would publish radical ideas. Diderot was not an established philosopher yet. It is well known that his financial situation had been precarious until 1747 and that the direction of the *Encyclopédie* had given him from this year on a modest, but steady income, as well as the reputation which he needed just as much. The *Encyclopédie* could not be published illegally, and Diderot had had to convince the conservative Chancellor d’Aguesseau to get a royal privilege for his editorial enterprise. He had managed to win over the *directeur de la Librairie du roi*, Chrétien-Guillaume de Lamoignon de Malesherbes, but this meant no security for him.

pensée politique de Diderot au temps de l’Encyclopédie: l’article ‘Droit naturel’”, in Deflers (ed.), *Diderot*, S. 157-180, here 174; Stenger, *Diderot*, 135; Jonathan I. Israel, *Enlightenment Contested. Philosophy, Modernity, and the Emancipation of Man, 1670-1752* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2006), 853; Andreas Heyer, *Materialien zum politischen Denken Diderots. Eine Werksmonographie* (Hamburg: Verlag Dr. Kovac, 2004), 145-179. Diderot for absolutism: Jacques Proust, *Diderot et l’Encyclopédie* (Paris: Colin, 1962), 20 (“Diderot est, sans contestation possible, un absolutiste, au moins dans toute la période de rédaction de l’*Encyclopédie*.”); Anthony Strugnell, *Diderot’s Politics. A Study of the Evolution of Diderot’s Political Thought after the Encyclopédie* (The Hague: Nijhoff, 1972), 8-9. Between these two extremes: Simone Goyard-Fabre, “Les idées politiques de Diderot au temps de l’Encyclopédie”, *Revue internationale de philosophie* 38 (1984), 91-119; Lester G. Crocker, “Diderot as a political philosopher”, *Revue internationale de Philosophie* 38 (1984), 120-139.

¹⁰ Lee, “Diderot.”

Famously, in 1749, he had been imprisoned for more than three months in Vincennes for his *Lettre sur les aveugles à l'usage de ceux qui voient*, whose sensualist speculations on the idea of God that blind people might have were considered offensive to religion. The police was very well informed about his manuscript writings, and considered him a “very witty, but extremely dangerous” young man because of his atheism,¹¹ and Diderot was careful enough not to publish compromising material again. Diderot was working hard to establish himself as a serious scholar and he rewrote the *Lettre sur les aveugles* in order to turn it into a rather innocuous critique of certain aesthetic theories.¹² Until the end of his life, he would pen many daring writings, but mainly for the drawer, or for posthumous publication, including several of his most popular texts now (*Jacques le fataliste*, *Le Rêve d'Alembert*, *Le Neveu de Rameau*). Other audacious texts he would publish as a ghost-writer (for Raynal's *History of the Two Indies*) or – like his contributions to Grimm's *Correspondance littéraire* – propagate them only in manuscripts for a very limited public at foreign princely courts, mostly in Germany and eastern Europe.¹³

In the first volume of the *Encyclopédie*, to which he prefixed a flowery dedication to War Minister Antoine René d'Argenson, Diderot published two articles on political authority, the famous “Autorité politique” and the much shorter “Autorité, pouvoir, puissance, empire”. In both, Diderot underlines the limited character of any legitimate rule and justifies it with the fact that God is above man. The article “Autorité, pouvoir, puissance, empire” reads: “There is no authority without law; there are no laws that confer unlimited authority. Every power

¹¹ Bibliothèque nationale de France, Département des manuscrits, NAF 10781, folio 147.

¹² Wilson, *Diderot*, 73-129.

¹³ On the *Correspondance littéraire* see Kirill Abrosimov, *Aufklärung jenseits der Öffentlichkeit. Friedrich Melchior Grimms Correspondance littéraire (1753-1773) zwischen der “République des lettres” und europäischen Fürstehöfen* (Ostfildern: Thorbecke, 2014).

[*pouvoir*] knows limits. There is no power [*puissance*] that should not be subject to God's."¹⁴

In the article “Autorité politique” Diderot states:

[...] man should not and cannot submit himself [*se donner*] wholly and without conditions to another man, because he has a Master who is superior to all and to whom he belongs wholly. It is God, whose power over the creature is always immediate [...]. He permits, for the common good and the preservation of society, that men establish among themselves a hierarchical order [*un ordre de subordination*], that they obey one of their own: but he would have this done reasonably and with moderation, and not blindly and without conditions, lest the creature should usurp the prerogatives of the Creator.¹⁵

The princely rule [*autorité*] is “limited by the laws of nature and of the state”, he insists. Diderot emphasises the difference between France, where the king rules according to the laws, and “Turkey”, where an “absolute lord” [*un maître absolu*] follows his whims. Diderot further explains that government is established by men through a contract. Therefore, political authority is not a possession of the king. For this reason, the sovereign has no right to change the form of government. The contract has clauses that limit the king’s power. Diderot emphasises that the king “may not dispose of his subjects without their consent.”¹⁶

The contract also establishes a whole series of duties for the subjects (and here it should be emphasised that Diderot does not write of “citoyens” but of “sujets”). Like the rulers, the subjects have no right to change the form of rule – in the French case, about which Diderot is obviously writing, absolute monarchy – or the succession to the throne. Even if the king is

¹⁴ Denis Diderot, “Autorité, pouvoir, puissance, empire,” in idem (ed.), *Encyclopédie ou Dictionnaire raisonné des sciences, des arts et des métiers*, vol. 1. (Paris 1751), here quoted from URL: <https://artflsrv03.uchicago.edu/philologic4/encyclopedie1117/navigate/1/5133/>.

¹⁵ Denis Diderot, “Autorité politique”, in idem (ed.), *Encyclopédie*, URL: <https://artflsrv03.uchicago.edu/philologic4/encyclopedie1117/navigate/1/5134/>

¹⁶ Ibid.

“unjust” and “violent,” they have no right whatsoever to disobey him. The only legitimate “remedy” in this case is to “appease the king through obedience” and to pray to God. The king is the image of God on earth and there is therefore no right to resist his authority in any case.

At the end of the article “Autorité politique”, Diderot uses the example of Henry IV of France to illustrate how the king should relate to his subjects. Henry IV is praised as a paternalistic ruler who seeks advice from his subjects and does not simply expect blind consent. At the same time, however, Diderot emphasises that “in the case where reason is so obviously on the side of the sovereign,” the latter has the right “to leave his subjects no choice and to expect obedience from them.”¹⁷ Henry IV is approvingly quoted as having legitimately demanded such obedience from his subjects: “I have drawn up this edict [of Nantes]; I want it to be obeyed. My will should suffice as a reason [...]. I am the king. I speak as the king. I want to be obeyed.”¹⁸ Diderot suggests here that the French king is absolute in a certain sphere of competence and in terms of the general good.

These theses were anything but original. That political authority is bound to both divine and man-made laws and that any legitimate power is limited were considered established truths in early modern France. The assertion of the limited character of legitimate political power, its bondage to fundamental laws as well as the necessity of the subjects’ consent if their property and person are to be disposed of, can hardly be understood as a critique of the French absolute monarchy. This impression may only arise if one follows the caricature that has long been cultivated under the keyword “absolutism”. In seventeenth- and eighteenth-century France, there was a large consensus that royal rule is absolute only in a certain prerogative sphere and that it is subject to both the ancient constitution of the realm and to God. In the eyes of the French, the unwritten constitution guaranteed, among other things, the inviolability of the

¹⁷ Ibid. (“Dans les cas où la raison est si visiblement du côté du souverain, qu’il a droit d’ôter à ses sujets la liberté du choix, & de ne leur laisser que le parti de l’obéissance.”).

¹⁸ Ibid. (“J’ai fait l’édit ; je veux qu’il s’observe. Ma volonté devrait servir de raison ; on ne la demande jamais au prince, dans un état obéissant. Je suis roi. Je vous parle en roi. Je veux être obéi.”).

property of subjects, which is why only the Estates General were considered competent to introduce new taxes. Contrary to the popular cliché about French absolutism, political theorists largely shared these ideas. That kingship was subject to fundamental laws was, in the eyes of the early modern French people, a cornerstone of their political order: it made the difference between their monarchy and “Turkish” despotism – a topos adopted by Diderot in the *Encyclopédie*, as we have seen.¹⁹ The distinction between legitimate and illegitimate authority and the idea that only the former comes from God was by no means as daring as some scholars portray it: as John Lough has shown, Le Franc de Pompignan, Bishop of Le Puy, later Archbishop of Vienne and opponent of Voltaire, followed the same interpretation of Paul’s Letter to the Romans as Diderot, and this idea was defended just as much by the Assembly of French Clergy in 1765.²⁰ The proximity between Diderot’s and *parlementaire* ideas thus does not result from his taken-over of a militant and radical theory, but rather from the fact that the judges of the Parlement were not conceiving their protestations as an opposition to absolute monarchy and were legitimising them by following established constitutional theory.

The short article “Autorité, pouvoir, puissance, empire” is another clue showing that the ideas presented in “Autorité politique” were not as daring as suggested in parts of historiography. This was assigned by the editors to the category “grammaire,” by which was meant that the article contains ordinary definitions of terms. Precisely because they make no claim to originality, reading such “grammaire” articles can be profitable: they show which topoi were established in Ancien Régime France. That political authority was bound to man-made laws and that any legitimate power was limited thus seems, according to the *Encyclopédie*, to be among the established truths that belong to the definition of these concepts, just like being bound to divine laws. It is also possible to identify the immediate source of Diderot’s assertions in this article and in “Autorité politique”: Abbé Gabriel Girard’s *Synonymes françois*, a

¹⁹ Nicholas Henshall, *The Myth of Absolutism. Change and Continuity in Early Modern European Monarchy* (London: Longman, 1992), 80-198.

²⁰ Lough, *Essays*, 442-3.

linguistic work published several times with royal privilege since 1718 and that can thus by no means be considered particularly political or daring.²¹

To be sure, some authors insisted in eighteenth-century France that God has instituted royal power directly and that the people played no role at all. This theory, sometimes called the “direct divine right theory”, had been formulated during the French Wars of Religion to assert that the people had no right of resistance. So, as Diderot develops a contract theory, his article did diverge from a part of the French political theory.²² This led the Jesuit *Journal de Trévoux* to criticise the article “Autorité politique”. The Jesuit journalist attacked above all the thesis that kingship arose from a contract between the people and the sovereign. The royal power had “a nobler and firmer origin”: “God is its author, as he is also its model. [...] Kings received their rule not from the Republic but from God.”²³

On the other hand, the emphasis placed by some scholars on this critique, used to demonstrate that Diderot was already politically radical in 1751, is greatly exaggerated. Though parts of scholarship claims that the article “Autorité politique” caused a “scandal,” the evidence is thin.²⁴ The contractualist theory of royal rule, which some critiques of the article “Autorité politique” opposed, may not have been that shocking after all. It was by no means an idea formulated first and foremost by supporters of revolutionary upheavals, but was rather an integral part of Roman law.²⁵ In the Régence, it had been a political doctrine officially endorsed by Philippe d’Orléans and the other ruling princes.²⁶ We should not exaggerate the contrast

²¹ Ibid., 427-429.

²² Paul-Alexis Mellet, *Les traités monarchomaques. Confusion des temps, résistance armée et monarchie parfaites* (Genève: Droz, 2007); Paul-Alexis Mellet (ed.), *Et de sa bouche sortait un glaive. Les monarchomaques au XVIIe siècle* (Genève: Droz, 2006); Eric Fuchs, *Le droit de résister. Le protestantisme face au pouvoir* (Genève: Éditions Labor et Fides, 1990); Sylvio Hermann De Franceschi, *La crise théologico-politique du premier âge baroque. Antiromanisme doctrinal, pouvoir pastoral et raison du prince ; le Saint-Siège face au prisme français (1606-1627)* (Rome: École française de Rome, 2009).

²³ *Journal de Trévoux*, vol. 1 of 1752, issue 3 (March 1752), 424-469.

²⁴ Diderot, Denis, *Œuvres politiques. Textes établis avec introductions, bibliographies, notes et relevé de variantes par Paul Vernière* (Paris: Garnier, 1963), 5-6; Lough, *Essays*, 439-462.

²⁵ “Lex regia” (Dig. I,4,1). I would like to thank Andreas Pečar for showing me this passage.

²⁶ Arlette Jouanna, *Le Sang des princes. Les ambiguïtés de la légitimité monarchique* (Paris: Gallimard, 2022), 218-223.

between both theories either: the direct divine right theory did not mean that kings had the power to dispose of the goods and life of their subjects according to their pleasure, and, as Diderot's article does not recognize any right of control or of resistance by the subjects whatsoever, the difference to the direct divine right theory is rather minimal in the end. Responding to critiques of the article "Autorité politique," Diderot and d'Alembert could easily cite from statements of the highest court of justice, the *Parlement de Paris*, and even from writings sponsored by King Louis XIV, to show that their position was completely orthodox.²⁷

Diderot's political ideas in the *Encyclopédie* were thus moderate in the French context. Indeed, Diderot's thought had a conservative tendency in the proper sense of the word. As appears in several *Encyclopédie* articles, Diderot placed a great emphasis on law and order. Diderot insisted that the subjects have no right to disobey royal laws. His main concern seems to have been political and social stability, which in his eyes could only be guaranteed in a monarchy by paternalistic kingship. This concern was reflected in a series of articles that the philosophe wrote for the *Encyclopédie*. The article "Cité" makes it clear that for Diderot, human beings renounce their own will with the establishment of political society: The "physical private beings" – that is, the private individuals – have "no more will" with their entry into a political community.²⁸ But with the growth of the "cité," vices and corruption automatically increase. As a result, it is very important to submit to the laws of the political community. Diderot therefore strongly condemns those who disturb public order.²⁹ The same concern for the preservation of public order is palpable in Diderot's article "Citoyen," which deals with republics. Diderot states that the citizen of a republic should always take the side of the established order: "In times of [political] turmoil, the citizen should support the party that

²⁷ [Bilain, Antoine,] *Traité des droits de la Reyne tres-chrestienne sur divers Estats de la Monarchie d'Espagne. Avec la Lettre du Roy Tres-Chrétien envoyée à la Reyne d'Espagne* (Grenoble: Robert Philippes, 1667), 129. See on that Lough, *Essays*, 434-436.

²⁸ Denis Diderot, "Cité," in idem (ed.), *Encyclopédie*, URL: <https://artflsrv03.uchicago.edu/philologic4/encyclopedie1117/navigate/3/2165/>.

²⁹ Ibid.

speaks in favour of the established system.”³⁰ He finds fault with the oath taken by the twenty-year-old (male) Athenians in antiquity because, in his eyes, the wording could provide a pretext for troublemakers. These swore: “I will obey according to the established customs and acknowledge what the people have hitherto *wisely* [emphasised by Diderot] decided.”³¹ According to Diderot, the term “wisely” could be misunderstood to mean that the new adult citizen promised to obey only the wise laws – and not the others. In this way, in his eyes, the binding character of the laws was weakened and order was left to the private discretion of the citizens.³²

Unlike in Jaucourt’s contributions to the *Encyclopédie*, there is no praise in Diderot’s articles of the separation of powers or of the English constitution, which Jaucourt valued so highly for its guarantee of personal liberties.³³ Only in republics does Diderot concede participation rights to the members of the political community; in these polities, but in these polities only, he claims quite classically that the greatest possible equality among citizens and the freedom of all are necessary for the preservation of public order.³⁴ In general, however, Diderot also followed the opinion, established since Greek antiquity, that republics were particularly unstable precisely because “perfect equality between their members is a chimera.”³⁵ He also represented the topos, established since Aristotle, that monarchies were always in danger of degenerating into tyrannies. According to this old cyclic conception of history, political systems inevitably approach their downfall over time. The best government is the one that lives the longest and keeps the peace: “Government is generally no different from animals:

³⁰ Denis Diderot, “Citoyen,” in idem (ed.), *Encyclopédie*, URL: <https://artflsrv03.uchicago.edu/philologic4/encyclopedie1117/navigate/3/2171/>

³¹ Ibid. (“receptis consuetudinibus parebo, & quascumque adhuc populus *prudenter* statuerit, amplectar”).

³² Ibid. (“Voilà un *prudenter*, qui abandonnant à chaque particulier le jugement des lois nouvelles, étoit capable de causer bien des troubles”).

³³ Louis de Jaucourt, “Liberté politique,” in Diderot (ed.), *Encyclopédie*, URL: <https://artflsrv03.uchicago.edu/philologic4/encyclopedie1117/navigate/5/634/>; idem, “Gouvernement”, in *ibid.*, URL: <https://artflsrv03.uchicago.edu/philologic4/encyclopedie1117/navigate/5/634/>; idem, “Monarchie limitée,” in *ibid.*, URL: <https://artflsrv03.uchicago.edu/philologic4/encyclopedie1117/navigate/5/634/>.

³⁴ Diderot, “Citoyen.”

³⁵ Ibid.

Every step in life is a step towards death. The best government is not the one that is immortal, but the one that lives the longest and the quietest.”³⁶

Diderot’s article “Autorité politique” may be considered rather conservative in comparison to significant parts of medieval and early modern natural law theory. In contrast with later French revolutionary thought, Diderot did not think in the *Encyclopédie* of natural, universal and inalienable rights that should be preserved in any society and thus shape social and political institutions in a uniform way. As his article “Droit naturel” makes clear, natural law was for him rather a set of moral principles to which the individual was to submit.³⁷ Contrary to what has sometimes been claimed in scholarship,³⁸ in the *Encyclopédie*, his thoughts were miles away from Locke’s *Two Treatises of Government*, which justified revolution, and it was even more conservative than common natural right theories denying to subjects the right of resistance, like Grotius’ and Pufendorf’s (these authors considered at least the possibility that princes and the estates might share authority). For example, the Swiss natural law scholar Jean-Jacques Burlamaqui (1694-1748), who stood in the tradition of Grotius and Pufendorf, considered the case where the contract of dominion between subjects and the prince was nullified by the latter through his own fault. Diderot, however, firmly rejected this possibility. This led Jacques Proust to conclude that Diderot had adopted Hobbes’ theory of sovereignty and refused any element that would have limited the powers of kings.³⁹

This conclusion may be exaggerated – there are major differences between Diderot’s emphasis on the rights of subjects and Hobbes’ Leviathan theory –, but Diderot was for sure not criticising absolute monarchy. His prudent stance appears even more clearly if we situate his thought within the scholastic tradition established in the high Middle Ages and pursued at

³⁶ Ibid. (“Il en est d’un gouvernement en général, ainsi que de la vie animale ; chaque pas de la vie est un pas vers la mort. Le meilleur gouvernement n’est pas celui qui est immortel, mais celui qui dure le plus long-tems & le plus tranquillement.”)

³⁷ Diderot, “Droit naturel,” <https://artflsrv04.uchicago.edu/philologic4.7/encyclopedie0922/navigate/5/606>.

³⁸ Goyard-Fabre, “Les idées politiques,” 113.

³⁹ Proust, *Diderot*, 20.

early modern Catholic universities: from Thomas Aquinas to Francisco Suárez, all major scholastic philosophers thought not only that political authority is created by a contract between the ruler and the people, but also that subjects have a right of resistance when suffering under despotism.⁴⁰ If Diderot departed from the mainstream political thought in early modern Catholic Europe, it was rather because he enhanced the inviolability of royal authority.

Yet Diderot's position shall not be understood as an expression of an attachment to tradition. It expressed rather an ideal common in the Enlightenment: a project of a harmonious society under the rule of a paternalistic king taking advice from his subjects and respecting their rights. This project was conceived as one of preservation from the "corruption" that stems from both despotism and factionalism, destroys the social bound and order, brings about civil wars, and causes the death of polities.

Diderot, proponent of physiocracy and councillor to princes (1760s)

Diderot did not pen any substantial statement on political theory in the following years. In the second half of the 1760s, however, his interest in political theory seems to have intensified and this had to do both with his own social advancement and with the emergence and growing influence of a new current of thought: physiocracy.

Since the first volume of the *Encyclopédie*, Diderot had very much climbed the social ladder. In 1765, he had been named a librarian of Empress Catherine II and had become a kind of official agent of the empress in Paris, playing a role complementary to that of the ambassador, as he wrote himself to his friend Falconet.⁴¹ It is not the place here to present in detail the numerous services rendered by Diderot to his principal patroness, the empress. Suffice to say that Diderot was a loyal and active client of this autocrat, who had come to power through a

⁴⁰ Francisco Suárez, *Defensio Fidei III. Principatus politicus o la soberania popular*, eds. E. Elorduy and L. Perena (Madrid: Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, 1965), 18-36; Jean-Paul, Coujou, "Political Thought and Legal Theory in Suárez," in Victor Salas (ed.), *Companion to Francisco Suárez* (Leiden: Brill, 2014), 29-71.

⁴¹ Letter to Falconet, 15 May 1767, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 730-740, here 735.

violent coup d'État. He spent a great deal of his time working for her and participated actively in the propaganda in her favour. In return, Diderot profited very much from the empress's patronage and by this way greatly increased both his symbolic and his financial capital. Among other honours, he sought and obtained nomination to the Saint-Petersburg Academy of Fine Arts.⁴² It is certainly impossible to estimate even approximately the total financial favours of the empress and indeed it is highly probable that what is preserved in the correspondence gives no more than a partial picture. However, adding up what we know from the letters that have been preserved, we can see, in the following years, Diderot and his family getting quite rich thanks to Catherine. He received, alongside a bust of Catherine, gold medals and a ring, 15,000 livres for his library,⁴³ a pension of at least 1,000 livres for the years 1765-6 in his role as librarian, an enormous gift of 50,000 livres,⁴⁴ then 3,000 roubles (converted into 12,600 livres),⁴⁵ and 2,000 livres.⁴⁶ Catherine paid the costs of the journey to Petersburg in full, in spite of the fact that she had given the philosopher the 3,000 roubles mentioned above for this purpose.⁴⁷ She rented a vast, modern and sumptuous apartment on the rue de Richelieu for Diderot and his wife.⁴⁸ She apparently paid the dowry of his daughter and thus permitted to contract a very advantageous marriage with the "chargé d'affaires" of the comte de Provence, the king's first brother and future king Louis XVIII.⁴⁹ She perhaps assumed the costs of his

⁴² Letter to the Imperial Academy of the arts in Saint-Petersburg, 5 February 1767, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 724.

⁴³ Wilson, *Diderot*, p. 466.

⁴⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 513.

⁴⁵ Letter to Mme Diderot, 9 April 1774, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 1221-1227, here 1221-1222.

⁴⁶ Letter to Catherine II, 29 June 1779, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 1303-1304; to Catherine II, 22 February 1774, in *ibid.*, 1210-1212, here 1212.

⁴⁷ Diderot pretends to reproach Catherine for shaking her confidence in doing him this favour, which is a delicate way of thanking her: to Catherine II, 13 September 1774, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 1255-1259, here 1256. The sum given by Catherine before his departure was 3,000 roubles, which Diderot converted into 12,600 livres: to Mme Diderot, 9 April 1774, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 1221-1227, here 1221-1222.

⁴⁸ Wilson, *Diderot*, 710.

⁴⁹ Johanna Borek, *Denis Diderot* (Reinbek: Rowohlt, 2000), 108. Whereas Diderot bring virtually no money into his own marriage in 1743, his daughter Denise was married in 1772 with a dowry of 30,000 livres and the prospect a life annuity of 1,125 livres and virtually all the properties of Diderot's sister at her death: Archives nationales, MC/RS//512 or MC/ET/LXXVI/297, "Contrat de mariage de Denis Diderot et Antoinette Champion, 26 octobre 1743"; Archives nationales, MC/RS//520 or MC/ET/LIII/489, "Contrat de mariage de Marie-Angélique Diderot (fille de Diderot) et Abel François Nicolas Caroillon, le 8 septembre 1772."

burial, greatly increased because his daughter and son-in-law did not skimp on pomp and also because it was necessary to convince the curate of the prestigious parish of Saint-Roch to bury the atheist on holy ground.⁵⁰ Certainly, Diderot's hopes of receiving 200,000 livres to produce a new encyclopaedia never materialised. In spite of this, thanks to his patroness, Diderot became affluent enough to finish his life in a certain luxury.⁵¹ His family climbed the social ladder, and Diderot's grandchildren were named *pairs de France*, obtaining the highest rank in French nobility.

Furthermore, Diderot was protected by several important personalities of the French court in those years. In the mid-1760s, Diderot (as he put it) "found protection with M. [Jean-Baptiste] Dubucq," First Clerk of the Ministry of the Navy and responsible for the Colonial Bureau.⁵² But it was above all Antoine de Sartine who played the role of Diderot's patron. From 1759 to 1774, Sartine was Lieutenant-General of Police of the Kingdom and, starting in 1763, Director of the *Librairie du roi* (the administration controlling book trade). He was therefore essentially the policeman and censor of the literary world and had a network of spies in his pay. In the historiography, Sartine appears mostly as Diderot's "friend", but it is clear that this was not a friendship among equals. In an unofficial manner, Diderot acted at least occasionally as a censor for Sartine.⁵³

In this context, Diderot showed himself increasingly confident that he might play an important role as a philosophical guide to people in power. In the preface to volume 8 of the *Encyclopédie* (1765), he expressed the hope that princes would soon follow enlightened principles.⁵⁴ His ideal of a paternalistic monarchy following the advice of (enlightened) subjects and respecting their rights, as he had expressed it in the *Encyclopédie*, seemed on the way of being realised.

⁵⁰ Stenger, *Diderot*, 703.

⁵¹ Pečar / Tricoire, "Diderot the Courtier?", 55.

⁵² Letter to Sophie Volland, 20 October 1765, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 541–3.

⁵³ Pečar / Tricoire, "Diderot the Courtier ?", 57-61.

⁵⁴ Antoine Lilti, *L'Héritage des Lumières. Ambivalences de la modernité* (Paris: Seuil, 2019), 263.

This hope was also linked to, and impacted by, the rising influence of physiocracy in the French state. As Goggi has shown, Diderot was strongly influenced by physiocracy in the second half of the 1760s.⁵⁵ For some years already, Diderot had been close to physiocrats like Anne-Robert Turgot, a friend of Malesherbes whom he had asked in 1759 to write some articles for the *Encyclopédie* and also to lobby the government in order to avoid a condemnation of the dictionary.⁵⁶ In the second half of the 1760s, Diderot acted as a broker on behalf of the physiocrat Pierre-Paul Le Mercier de La Rivière, whom he recommended warmly to the court of Saint-Petersburg, and whose work he praised very highly in his correspondence. In 1768, in his unofficial position as an advisor to royal censorship, he convinced Sartine to authorise Le Mercier de La Rivière's *L'Ordre naturel et essentiel des sociétés politiques*.⁵⁷ Already in 1767, he had written to his friend Falconet: "Le Mercier de La Rivière is the apostle of property, the basis of all good law; of liberty. He has found the secret of the happiness of empires [...] [here in the sense of a polity under a rule, D. T.]."⁵⁸

This unconditional praise for Le Mercier de La Rivière may seem surprising if one expects that Diderot's ideas prefigured modern liberal-democratic ideals. Like François Quesnay, Le Mercier de La Rivière rejected any form of checks and balances in politics; on the contrary, he actively endorsed the idea of legal despotism. For Le Mercier de La Rivière, political authority had to be absolute and uncontrolled. It was submitted only to divine laws. When Diderot praised Le Mercier de La Rivière, he seems to have concurred with him that the only check to royal power was to be the "evidence" of natural law.⁵⁹ This endorsement of Le Mercier de La Rivière's theory also contrasts with Lee's view of a pro-*parlementaire* Diderot.

⁵⁵ Goggi, *De l'Encyclopédie*, 346-424.

⁵⁶ Letter to Turgot, 21 January 1759, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 87.

⁵⁷ Letter to Falconet, 6 September 1768, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 848-877, here 851.

⁵⁸ Letter to Falconet, July 1767, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 741-748, here 746-747.

⁵⁹ Some years later, in "Observations," Diderot took a critical look on this theory: Denis Diderot, "Observations sur l'instruction de S.M.I. aux députés pour la confection des lois," in idem, *Textes politiques*, ed. Yves Benot (Paris: Éditions sociales, 1960), 79.

This seems to suggest that Diderot's thought experienced a radical turn under the influence of physiocracy.

Yet if one considers both Diderot's endorsement of a paternalistic monarchy model and the way he interpreted Le Mercier de La Rivière, we may come to a different conclusion. The kinship between the theory developed in "Autorité politique" and some pro-*parlementaire* writings had not stemmed from an active support of *parlementaire* struggles, but rather from a widely shared view that the French monarch, who was no despot, must respect the rights of his subjects and take their advice, while those subjects in turn must obey and have no right of resistance. The core of the physiocratic political project was the idea that the monarch was to follow natural laws and to reform France in order to make positive laws adequate to them. As Goggi has shown, Diderot read Le Mercier de La Rivière in the light of Dupont de Nemours' and Turgot's views. These latter physiocrats, contrary to Quesnay and Le Mercier de La Rivière, did not insist on "legal despotism" but rather on how the king could benefit from the advices of his subjects. While they did not question the royal monopoly of legislative power, they envisioned the creation of councils of landowners at the local and regional levels of society. There is strong evidence that Diderot was very favourable to such ideas.⁶⁰

To be sure, Diderot's optimism in the 1760s – concomitant with his endorsement of physiocracy – led him to put a somewhat different emphasis than in the early 1750s. In the *Encyclopédie*, he had in a classical humanist fashion insisted on the danger that monarchy might degenerate into despotism. He had held that royal power was limited not only by divine law – which is broadly similar to the physiocrats' insistence on the evidence of God-made natural laws –, but also by human-made laws, that is in the French context the ancient constitution of the realm. The influence of physiocratic theses meant that the ancient constitution of the realm could not be a point of reference anymore. Nevertheless, we should not overestimate the

⁶⁰ Goggi, *De l'Encyclopédie*, 346-424. Turgot's ideas: *Œuvres posthumes de M. Turgot, ou Mémoire de M. Turgot sur les Administrations provinciales* [...] (Lausanne [Paris?]: s.n., 1787).

discontinuities in Diderot's political thought. The praise for Le Mercier de La Rivière's system can be interpreted as a sign of a continuous support for a strong paternalistic royal power in the framework of a search for social stability and a just social order. Under the impression that "les lumières" made progress, of which his own social advancement and his role as a client of an empress and influential French courtiers was a sign, Diderot may have insisted more clearly than before on the benefits that could come from an enlightened absolute monarchy. Physiocracy may also have been attractive to him at this time because it gave philosophers a major role to play as councillor to princes, who were expected to follow reason and the law of nature.

Diderot in Russia: a radical turn?

Before the 1770s at least, then, there is no reason to think that Diderot has put into question the French absolute monarchy. In the French context, his political ideas were moderate and in the European context even rather conservative in the sense that he was much concerned with political stability and endorsed an absolute monarchical rule. Like many other Enlightenment philosophes, he advocated a paternalistic monarchy that was to listen to (enlightened) subjects and respect their rights, while they had to respect authority. This model was considered a good way to avoid the corruption of political systems, a natural tendency of all "ageing" polities. Diderot set some limits to royal authority in the *Encyclopédie*, but only in a way widely accepted in France, and even this fragile barrier to despotism disappeared in his statements in favour of physiocracy in the second half of the 1760s. He did not theorise any participation of subjects to power nor write about natural, universal and inalienable political rights. Nor did he accordingly acknowledge any right to disobedience or resistance. However, in the 1770s, his political ideas seem to have changed quite sharply, and the interpretation of Diderot as a radical political writer insists above all on the texts he penned in those years, that is – so the most common narrative says – after his travel to Saint-Petersburg in 1773–1774. According to this view, Diderot was

strongly disappointed by Catherine II and adopted democratic ideals.⁶¹ Another interpretation insists on the disappointment that Diderot felt after Turgot's fall in 1776, which led him to abandon his hopes of a reform by a paternalistic monarchy.⁶²

There is much to be said in favour of the thesis that Diderot experienced a radical turn around 1774. For sure, Diderot became critical of at least some aspects of physiocracy and expressed in several texts, some of which were published, a strong rejection of any kind of despotism, even an enlightened one. Occasionally, he went as far as to legitimise the uprisings of subjects whose right to happiness was disregarded by rulers. Some sentences read like a strong plea for democracy and a proto-revolutionary discourse. However, as we will see, this reading over-interprets some passages or fragments without considering with sufficient care what they proposed, whether they contradicted other fragments, whether they were written for publication, their function in a wider text, or the precise political context in which they were written or published.

To understand why Diderot distanced himself from physiocracy around 1770, it is important to look at Diderot's position within the French elites in those years. In late 1768, he had begun to frequent the extremely rich banker Jacques Necker, who had taken control of the Compagnie des Indes, and his wife.⁶³ In 1772, we find Diderot working behind the scenes for Necker. Thus, in early September 1772, Diderot invited Grimm to join him at the Necker residence in Saint-Ouen to discuss an "affair so serious" and apparently so delicate that he could not be more explicit in a letter that might fall into the wrong hands.⁶⁴ The following missive is

⁶¹ Jonathan Israel, *Democratic Enlightenment. Philosophy, Revolution and Human Rights, 1750-1790* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2011), 619–626. See also Stenger, *Diderot*, 306; Jacques Proust, "Diderot et l'expérience russe. Un exemple de pratique théorique au XVIIIe siècle," *Studies on Voltaire and the Eighteenth Century* 151-155 (1976), 1777–1800; Isabelle Deflers, "Diderots Auseinandersetzung mit dem 'aufgeklärten Despotismus' Friedrichs II.," in Deflers (ed.), *Diderot und die Macht*, 61–82, here 76–78.

⁶² Goggi, *De l'Encyclopédie*, 458.

⁶³ Kenta Ohji, "Raynal, Necker et la Compagnie des Indes. Quelques aspects inconnus de la genèse et de l'évolution de l'Histoire des deux Indes," in Gilles Bancarel (ed.), *Raynal et ses réseaux* (Paris: Honoré Champion, 2011), 105–82, here 112–115; letter to Mme Necker, December 1768, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 926-928; to Mme de Maux, around the 10 August 1769, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 961-962; to Sophie Volland, 23 August 1769, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 965-967, here 967.

⁶⁴ Letter to Grimm, 2 September 1772, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 1122-1123, here 1123.

filled with code words which unfortunately cannot all be deciphered now.⁶⁵ Yet what arises clearly from these letters is that Diderot and Grimm were intriguing on behalf of Necker, who had political ambitions and was launching a campaign to influence public opinion.⁶⁶ The patronage of the Necker couple may have played a role in persuading Diderot to dissociate himself from physiocracy in the late 1760s. Necker was in a conflict with some physiocrats and Mme Necker's salon became a place where people hostile to physiocracy met. Thus, Diderot defended Necker against Abbé André Morellet, the physiocratic writer in the service of Minister of the Navy Praslin, and the work of Abbé Ferdinando Galiani, who was contradicting physiocrats.⁶⁷ In the following years, Necker's main political rival was to be Turgot, a physiocrat with whom Diderot had long been in contact with, as we have seen.

Most famously, above all two groups of Diderot's writings bear the mark of a turn from physiocratic thought and of an explicit critique of despotism: passages about Russia and texts about the American Revolution, which should be considered separately. The narrative that tells the story of a radicalisation of Diderot during his stay at Catherine's court considers the former group of sources to be indicative of a turn towards democracy in Diderot's thought. There is some truth in this interpretation. There is no doubt that in some texts Diderot criticised Catherine II repeatedly for being a despot. Famously, the most impressive of Diderot's writings in this respect is "Observations sur l'instruction de S.M.I. aux députés pour la confection des lois," better known as "Observations sur le nakaz," written during his stay in Saint Petersburg or on the way back to France. In "Observations," Diderot criticizes the empress with astonishing frankness for keeping all legislative power for herself, condemns despotism repeatedly and

⁶⁵ Letter to Grimm, 7 October 1772, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 1133-1135.

⁶⁶ Letter to Mme Necker, 15 October 1772, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 1139; to Mme Necker, end of October 1772, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 1141. On Necker's campaigns to influence public opinion: Léonard Burnand, *Les Pamphlets contre Necker. Médias et imaginaire politique au XVIIIe siècle* (Paris: Garnier, 2008).

⁶⁷ On Diderot and the Neckers in the late 1760s: letter to Mme Necker, December 1768, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 926-928; to Mme de Maux, around the 10 August 1769, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 961-962; to Sophie Volland, 23 August 1769, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 965-7, here 967. On Diderot and Galiani: To Sophie Volland, 11 September 1769, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 972-975, here 973-974; to Sartine, 13 October 1769, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 982.

suggests the establishment of a monarchy in which representatives of the nation would convene, play an important role in the legislative process and control the conformity of the monarch's actions with laws. He approves of the British political system.⁶⁸ He explicitly rejects Quesnay's and Le Mercier de La Rivière's idea that the evidence of natural law is the only legitimate check to royal authority.⁶⁹ Diderot seems thus to depart from the political system he advocated both in "Autorité politique" and in his later endorsements of physiocracy.

By closer look, however, even in "Observations", the political system proposed by Diderot present some continuities with the theory he had developed in "Autorité politique". First of all, already in the *Encyclopédie*, Diderot had clearly opposed despotism; for him, the monarch was bound to fundamental laws and had a moral duty to convene his subjects to hear their advice. Second, while Diderot states in "Observations" that "there can be no other real legislator than the people", he seems by that to have in mind a kind of social contract by which fundamental laws are established. After this, he only envisages that "representatives of the nation" gather every five year to judge whether "the sovereign" has respected these laws. As Yves Benot rightly points out, Diderot thus does not suggest a parliamentary regime, and his ideas about political representation and participation are even less daring than Turgot's. Neither does Diderot say that subjects have a right of resistance.⁷⁰ For him, the original legislative power belongs to the people, but after the establishment of monarchy, it is exercised by "the sovereign" (a term that indicates that the nation is no longer sovereign but rather bound by laws to obedience). The gathering of representatives of the nation every five years reminds of the ideal of a monarch – embodied in "Autorité politique" by Henry IV – taking advice from his subjects and respecting their constitutional rights.

"Observations" is furthermore a text that is difficult to interpret. It is actually barely a text, but rather a series of notes on Catherine's instruction, and these fragments are in a great

⁶⁸ Diderot, "Observations", 61-62, 71-74, 86, 176.

⁶⁹ Diderot, "Observations", 79.

⁷⁰ Diderot, "Observations," 61-62.

disorder – a fact that can be easily overlooked because the version that was printed in Diderot’s *Œuvres complètes* has been strongly reshaped by his heirs. The content is not always clear and may present some contradictions. For example, while Diderot pleads for an end of the privileges of nobility in some fragments, he claims in another that “[i]n France, abolishing privileges, rights, distinctions, etc., some of which have been granted as rewards for services and others acquired at a cost, would mean committing an incredible number of injustices” – a moderate Enlightenment stance, at least for the French context.⁷¹ The main problem in interpreting this source is to understand for whom it has been written. While it is addressed to Catherine, it is unclear whether Diderot really intended to send it to her. We can exclude one scenario, however, and that is what matters here most: Diderot did not plan to publish it. He never made any effort to turn it into a single text that he could have shown to a public, indeed even to Catherine.⁷²

The fragments usually known as “Mélanges pour Catherine II,” which were written in Russia in the context of his audiences with the empress, are a further sign that we should be careful in assessing the scope of Diderot’s turn towards more radical ideas. The content of these fragments is rather ambivalent. While in some fragments Diderot enjoins, in a way similar to “Observations,” the empress to erect barriers against the despotism of her successors, in others he also suggests means to strengthen monarchical power.⁷³ In one fragment, he condemns markedly the British parliamentary system.⁷⁴

The contrast with the “Observations” are even greater when it comes to Diderot’s printed works of the 1770s. In the passage on Russia published in the third edition of the *History*

⁷¹ Suggests the suppression of privileges: Diderot, “Observations”, 82, 97. Quote: *ibid.*, 83. See also p. 75, in which Diderot pleads for an inviolability of privileges belonging to each “ordre de citoyens.”

⁷² Georges Dulac, “Les ‘Observations sur le nakaz’: de nouveaux choix éditoriaux,” *Diderot Studies* 33 (2013), 107-151; Jean-Christophe Rebejkow, “Diderot et les tentatives réformatrices de Catherine II,” *Zeitschrift für französische Sprache und Literatur* 126 (2016), 68-104.

⁷³ Diderot, “Mélanges philosophiques, historiques, etc. Année 1773 depuis le 15 octobre jusqu’au 3 décembre même année,” in *idem*, *Œuvres*, vol. 3: *Politique* (Paris: Robert Laffont, 1995), 203-407, here 210.

⁷⁴ Diderot, “Mélanges,” 209.

of the Two Indies (1780), Diderot expresses positions about Catherine's empire and authority that are much more moderate than those in the manuscript fragments that we use to call "Observations sur le nakaz." To be sure, at the beginning of the chapter, he strongly rejects despotism, even an enlightened one, and claims – like in "Observations" – that a succession of three enlightened despots would be "the most terrible scourge" because it would get subjects used to slavery. He exhorts the peoples of Europe not to allow the monarchs do to anything, even the good, against their "general will." That said, however, this chapter then takes a wholly different direction. Diderot explains that all concurs to make impossible the civilisation and liberation of Russia: the general barbarism of the Russian population, its abuse of alcoholic drinks, climate, the enormous extent of Russian territory, the difficulty of travelling, the incompetence and corruption of judges and the power of landowners, who would never permit the abolition of serfdom. Diderot claims that a sovereign alone cannot change his country very much. While Catherine has made many laudable efforts, these cannot modify Russian society in depth and in the long run. This text reads in the end like a justification for the non-introduction of freedom by Catherine. Accordingly, the chapter ends with following sentences: "Such are the difficulties which we have found to oppose the civilisation of the Russian Empire. If Catherine II succeeds in overcoming them, we will have made of her courage and genius the most magnificent praise, and if she succumbs in this great project, perhaps the best of apologies."⁷⁵ This raises the question of whether the strong critique of despotism at the beginning of the chapter might not be sort of a *captatio benevolentiae*: as the French public usually rejected despotism resolutely, and thus could be expected to be sceptical of Catherine's authority, any skilful apology of the empress would have to first disapprove Russian despotism to explain in a second step that, unfortunately, it is necessary, at least in any near future.

⁷⁵ Guillaume-Thomas Raynal, *Histoire philosophique et politique des établissements et du commerce dans les deux Indes*, 10 vols. (Genève: Jean-Léonard Pellet, 1780), vol. 10, 39-50 (Livre XIX, Chapitre 2: "Sur le gouvernement," quote p. 50).

The narrative that tells the story of a radicalisation of Diderot after his trip in Saint Petersburg presents thus a number of flaws. It does not take into consideration that the “Observations” are a series of notes not intended for any public and even partly contradictory, and that these fragments do not propose a parliamentary regime; and it ignores the ambiguities of “Mélanges” and the apologetic character of the chapter on Russia in the *History of the Two Indies*. Furthermore, the standard narrative obliterates the fact that Diderot never expressed disappointment about Catherine. Quite the contrary; he was persistently enthusiastic about her.⁷⁶ This casts strong doubts on the context in which Diderot is supposed to have changed his mind about such issues as the dangers of despotism, the necessity of intermediary bodies and the necessity of citizens to participate in legislative work. Obviously, Diderot still saw himself as a councillor of the empress rather than as a man fighting in the public sphere and undertaking autonomous political actions. Correspondingly, Diderot repeatedly expressed the idea that good legislation was to come from the advice of philosophers and, still defended, in his apology of Seneca, the ideal of the philosopher at court against criticisms by Rousseau and others.⁷⁷ There are thus good reasons to think that despite his claims that enlightened despotism may cause great harm in the long run, Diderot never abandoned totally the ideal of a paternalistic monarchy listening to (enlightened) subjects, which was a most common vision among *philosophes*. It is important to bear in mind that in the late phase of his literary career, Diderot, besides working on the *History of the Two Indies*, was above all writing for princes and princesses via Grimm’s *Correspondance littéraire*. Contrary to journalists and pamphleteers like the lawyers attacking Maupeou in 1771–1774 or Jacques-Pierre Brissot in the 1780s, Diderot does not seem not to have felt the need to start broad campaigns to change public opinion via the newspapers and

⁷⁶ Pečar / Tricoire, “Diderot the Courtier?”, 53.

⁷⁷ On the role of the philosophes in indirectly giving laws to polities: “Sages de la terre, philosophes de toutes les nations, c’est à vous seuls à faire des loix”: Guillaume-Thomas Raynal, *Histoire philosophique et politique des établissements et du commerce dans les deux Indes*, 10 vols. (Geneva: s.n., 1781), vol. 1, 103. On the *Essai sur Sénèque*: Pečar / Tricoire, “Diderot the Courtier ?”, 38-43.

pamphlets. Despite his critique of “enlightened despotism”, he still, like in his physiocratic phase, conceived of himself as a councillor to sovereigns.

Supporting French foreign policy, admiring a young nation: Diderot and America

The second major argument in favour of a turn to political radicalism in the 1770s is Diderot’s approval of the American Revolution.⁷⁸ There is indeed no doubt that, in his defence of the American rebels against British rule, Diderot claimed that the governments have been instituted in order to serve the interests of society and that nations have always the right to change the constitution of their polity if they wish to. This he asserted not only in manuscripts, but also in print, most famously in a chapter of the best-selling third edition of *The History of the Two Indies*.⁷⁹

Yet while this passage might be considered a sign of Diderot’s radicalisation, another reading is also possible. On closer look, the chapter of *The History of the Two Indies* is not a plea for democracy. Diderot states that natural equality, even in the legal sense, is a chimera. The natural inequality of human beings is necessary and eternal and “nothing can be done about it” except correcting abuses.⁸⁰ Again, Diderot does not seem to have any natural, universal and inalienable rights in view, and does not speak of the necessity to maintain natural freedom and equality in society.⁸¹ Diderot displays instead a marked pessimism here: nature itself has sowed the seeds of tyranny and as a result “the history of civilised man is only the history of his misery.”⁸² This position contrasts strongly with natural law theories that provided for the main justification of both the American and the French revolutions.⁸³ It was because American and

⁷⁸ Kerautret, “Diderot.”

⁷⁹ Raynal, *Histoire des deux Indes* (Geneva: Jean-Léonard Pellet, 1780), vol. 9, 249-253 (livre 18).

⁸⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 250.

⁸¹ Dan Edelstein notes the influence on Diderot of the physiocrats’ “dangerous ignorance of natural rights”: Dan Edelstein, *On the Spirit of Rights* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2019), 85-90.

⁸² *Ibid.*, p. 250.

⁸³ On the importance of natural law for the American and the French revolutions see Edelstein, *On the Spirit of Rights*, 143-192, and my forthcoming “La Cité de Dieu des patriotes. La pensée théocratique des Lumières et les origines religieuses de la Révolution française,” *French Historical Studies* 46/3 (2023).

French rebels claimed that natural law is superior to any human-made constitution that they were able to legitimise the instauration of a new political order. Diderot seems in this chapter of *The History of the Two Indies* far away from endorsing this idea, even if it would have been almost obvious to defend the core ideas of the American revolutionaries.

Diderot does not explain in this chapter how abuses might be corrected and how the condition of man in society improved. There is no consideration of the optimal political system. Instead, he proceeds by giving arguments in favour of the right of the inhabitants of the thirteen colonies to declare independence. The argument that peoples have the right to change their constitution is not embedded in a plea for democracy, but rather supports the secession of the colonies from their motherland. Correspondingly, the narrator constantly calls on “les Anglais” in the second person plural and the bulk of the text is made up of answers to British arguments: he argues that the state of British finance does not allow them to wage war; the Americans are a separate people from the British; they are not ungrateful and have valiantly fought for the British in the last war; a motherland should concede freedom to a colony when it is mature; the trade acts are unjust; the colonies are unnecessary to Britain’s strength and security; and it is possible to stop the present war without dishonour.⁸⁴

The thesis according to which a people can change its constitution was thus an answer to a common British objection to the American declaration of independence. There is no evidence that it was meant as a part of a general plea for democracy. We must be prudent not to over-interpret this chapter by reading it in the light of the French Revolution. Justifying the rebellion of the thirteen colonies was not a radical stance in the late 1770s and early 1780s in France, as the French king was waging war to support them. French publicists indeed were expected to justify French support for the American rebels and Diderot was doing exactly that. The idea that peoples have the right to change their constitution may have had revolutionary

⁸⁴ Raynal, *Histoire des deux Indes* (Geneva: Jean-Léonard Pellet, 1780), vol. 9, p. 252-271.

potential. Yet what matters here is that Diderot did not follow its consequences to its end, did not apply it to France, and thus did not suggest changes in the French political order. Indeed, as Goggi has shown, Diderot had theoretical reasons to think that the American revolution was not a model for France: he thought that such a happy revolution was only possible in a young, still uncorrupted nation.⁸⁵ Like Aristotle and the dominant Western tradition of political theory, the “dernier Diderot” had still a cyclic conception of history – as is shown among others by his *Essai sur Sénèque* –⁸⁶ and was not advocating a particular political regime that would fit to any polity. When it came to France, Diderot’s views were much more gloomy, and this pessimism stemmed largely from the political events of the first half of the 1770s.

Diderot and the Maupeou “revolution”

It appears thus clearly that Diderot did not change decisively his ideas about the optimal political system between the early 1750s and the mid-1770s, but rather placed the emphasis on different elements of his discourse. To understand why the latter Diderot developed more clearly than before a critique of any kind of despotism, it is important to take into consideration the new political context in France in the years 1771–1774. The narrative that credits Diderot’s trip to Petersburg with the merit of having disillusioned him about enlightened despotism does not consider that he began to criticise enlightened despotism more openly not in 1773-1774, but rather already at the latest in 1772, that is before his stay at the Russian court. This is important to bear in mind in order to have a less anachronistic idea of Diderot’s statements. The very fragments Diderot wrote for Catherine, or at least in the context of his conversations with her, provide some clues: in some of them, Diderot rejected strongly the suppression of the *Parlement de Paris* by Chancellor Maupeou in 1771. While Diderot expressed contempt for the *Parlement de Paris*, in both “Mélanges pour Catherine II” and “Observations sur le nakaz,” its

⁸⁵ Goggi, *De l’Encyclopédie*, 528-536.

⁸⁶ Diderot, *Essai sur les règnes de Claude et de Néron*, vol. 2, 151.

suppression meant for him the instauration of despotism in France and this even appears to have been for him a real trauma.⁸⁷

The *Parlement* was not a mere court of justice; it checked the constitutionality of laws, that is, it stated whether royal *lettres patentes* and *édits* were in conformity with the (unwritten) ancient constitution of the realm. In Diderot's view, by abolishing this institution, Maupeou was removing the most important element that made the difference between French monarchy and the Turkish or Russian despotism: the boundness of royal power to fundamental laws, which was at the core of the distinction between monarchy and despotism in "Autorité politique" and in early modern French thought in general. Diderot was by far not the only writer who was terrified by this prospect. Maupeou's "revolution" from above – the term was commonly used – provoked a public outcry not only among the *parlementaires*, but also of many journalists and pamphleteers, and a strong opposition of some princes of royal blood. All these oppositional activities have been termed a "rehearsal of the French Revolution". Whereas this is missing the point about what was so radical about 1789, it was for sure a moment in which ministerial authority was vigorously put into question.⁸⁸

It is this revolution from above – that modified strongly the French political system and attacked the ancient constitution of the realm –, and not Diderot's stay in Russia, that may have risen his awareness about the danger of despotism and the necessity to craft a political system that makes tyranny impossible. In "Observations" he insists, in a Montesquieu-like fashion, on the necessity of *pouvoirs intermédiaires* representing both the interests of different estates and of the nation at large.⁸⁹ Whereas Diderot had generally speaking an utterly negative opinion of the judges of the *Parlement de Paris*, after the dismantling of the ancient constitution of the realm of France by Chancellor Maupeou in 1771, he approved of strong checks to royal power

⁸⁷ Diderot, "Mélanges," 212-226; Diderot, "Observations," 77-81, 121

⁸⁸ Durrant Echeverria, *The Maupeou Revolution. A Study in the History of Libertarianism* (Baton Rouge: Louisiana State University Press, 1985).

⁸⁹ Diderot, "Observations," 74.

and regretted that the *Parlement* had not defended the constitution with more vigour.⁹⁰ Doing this, he was not anticipating the French Revolution, but rather endorsing core political ideas from the so-called “parti patriotique,” that is the supporters of the *Parlement de Paris*. In a further sign of Diderot’s alignment with the “parti patriotique,” the Prince of Conti, the most determined opponent to Maupeou among the princes of royal blood, gratified him with a pension of 1000 livres yearly in 1774.⁹¹

Yet this context induced rather an inflexion in Diderot’s political discourse than a change in his thought. His support for the “parti patriotique” was totally in line with the monarchy model he had formulated in the *Encyclopédie*. The point about the rejection of Maupeou’s revolution was defending the ancient constitution of the realm, not introducing any new political order. The problem that Diderot saw was that the *parlements* had been unable to stop tyranny. The French government was destroying the ancient political system and nothing or nobody could prevent it from doing so. Such ideas may not have been consensual in France in the 1770s, but they were not as radical as is sometimes believed in modern scholarship. The conviction that Maupeou acted tyrannically and that the ancient constitution of the realm was the binding legal order was widely shared in French society.

It is also striking that Diderot, for all his hostility towards despotism, did not denounce Maupeou’s coup publicly. How can be this explained? Besides a general reluctance to position himself publicly in French politics, at least under his own name, Diderot’s relationships with some mighty courtiers might offer a clue. In “Mélanges pour Catherine,” he reports that he had considered writing a pamphlet against Maupeou but had renounced it because it is unwise for a citizen to take risks without having the prospect to succeed.⁹² And indeed, Diderot had much to lose by attacking Maupeou’s radical reform. Around 1770, he had begun to pay court

⁹⁰ Echeverria, *The Maupeou Revolution*, 229-231, 237.

⁹¹ Pierre Terver, *Le dernier prince de Conti à l’Isle-Adam (1776-1789)* (Pontoise: Société historique et archéologique de Pontoise, 1989), 19. I would like to thank Simon Dagenais for this information.

⁹² Diderot, “Mélanges,” 224.

intensively to a whole series of influential patrons in order to obtain a dowry that would allow him to marry his daughter advantageously. His potential son-in-law Caroillon de Vandeuil being demanding for the dowry, Diderot solicited money not only from Necker, from Jean-Baptiste Devaines, who had important responsibilities in the finance administration, and from the Intendant-General of Finances Trudaine, but also from the Duke of Aiguillon, the very Minister of Foreign Affairs who had come to power after the fall of Choiseul in 1770 and was collaborating with Maupeou.⁹³ Diderot seems to have obtained from Aiguillon some substantial advantage for his son-in-law, for Caroillon de Vandeuil showed himself very satisfied with an interview that Diderot had arranged.⁹⁴ Aiguillon, moreover, maintained a foreign policy more favourable to Russia than Choiseul's, which fitted Diderot's personal situation as a client of the empress. Aiguillon's patronage explains a fact that is known but nevertheless curiously neglected and left unexplained by Diderot's biographers: at St. Petersburg, Diderot did not only show himself devoted to Catherine II, he also served as an unofficial diplomatic agent for the French Foreign Minister.⁹⁵ A section of the "Mélanges pour Catherine II" may indeed have been part of this diplomatic offensive.⁹⁶ As a client of Aiguillon, Diderot did not dare to criticise Maupeou publicly.

What changed in the 1770s were not so much Diderot's ideas about the optimal political system, but rather his assessment of the chances that it might be realised. Maupeou's revolution had shocked him, and – as Goggi has shown – Turgot's failure as a finance minister in 1776 may have further induced him to believe that a return of Henry IV's paternalistic monarchy was improbable in the context of a corrupted and "aged" society like France. For this reason, towards the end of his life, Diderot held that a succession of civil wars and revolutions was to be

⁹³ Letter to his sister Denise, 27 August 1771, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 1080.

⁹⁴ Letter to Grimm, 29 April 1772, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 1109; to Grimm, 18 October 1772, in Diderot, *Correspondance*, 1140.

⁹⁵ Wilson thinks that Diderot "found himself caught up in the diplomatic manoeuvrings of great powers, perhaps very much against his will.": Wilson, *Diderot*, 635-636.

⁹⁶ Diderot, "Mélanges," 227-232.

expected in France. He repeatedly depicted France's future in terrible terms, insisting on the upcoming bloodshed. Simultaneously, he expressed the hope that this cycle of intestine troubles might lead to a regeneration of the French monarchy, as it had in seventeenth-century England.⁹⁷ Yet this hope is not to be mixed up with a "revolutionary choice." Even in the time of the American or Genevan revolutions, he did not conceive of revolution as an option that one may choose actively, but rather as a catastrophe that a society might suffer. His conception of revolutions was not modern, but rather the expression of the classical cyclic vision of history already present in the *Encyclopédie*: politics grow, age, decay, die – and sometimes resurrect from their ashes.

Conclusion

If we apply the two criteria mentioned at the beginning of this article – the degree to which an author puts the political and social order of his own country into question and the degree to which he expresses this position publicly, starts a propaganda campaign or is politically active to realise this programme –, Diderot can be deemed a moderate Enlightenment *philosophe*. Yet his political thought shall not be defined only *ex negativo*, in contrast to radical democratic ideas. Diderot had a real ideal, which he shared with most of the Enlightenment *philosophes*: that of a paternalistic monarchy based on a social contract with the subjects, respecting their rights as defined in this contract (the constitution) and taking their advice, that is both the advice of enlightened people and of consultative representative assemblies. While in different periods of his life he insisted on different aspects of this ideal, was more or less optimistic or pessimistic about its realisation, and used varied rhetoric, it represented a thread through his political thought and conferred a certain coherence to his political statements.

⁹⁷ Goggi, *De l'Encyclopédie*, 481-528.

There is no evidence that Diderot proposed any significant changes to the French political system during his career. As indicated in the first volume of the *Encyclopédie*, in the early 1750s, he was very much concerned with political stability and endorsed the model of a paternalistic monarchy. In “Autorité politique” he claimed that political authority is bound by divine and human laws, but did not concede any right of resistance to the subjects, a rather conservative stance in comparison to many well-known natural law theories of the Middle Ages and early modern times. His ideas were in the mainstream of French political thought, that also considered monarchical power to be both absolute and limited by both divine law and the ancient constitution of the realm. Diderot insisted on the fact that the king had to take advice from his subjects and to respect their rights, whereas they had to obey. This was for him a way to avoid the quasi-natural evils of factionalism and despotism that tend to grow when a polity ages and lead to its decay and destruction.

In the late 1760s, Diderot praised a physiocratic political theory (Le Mercier de La Rivière’s) that emphasised “legal despotism” and identified natural law as the only legitimate check to royal power. He thus approved publicly of thinkers who discarded the ancient constitution of the realm. Yet Diderot still had – like physiocrats like Turgot – a political system in mind in which representative assemblies would advise the sovereign and in which the latter would endorse the rights of his subjects, or rather reform France to make these rights a reality in positive laws.

The “dernier Diderot” did not envisage other political institutions for France, even in his most radical writing, the “Observations sur le nakaz.” It is true that he became more afraid than before of the evils of despotism, especially after the dismantling of the French constitution between 1771 and 1774. Like many of his fellow Frenchmen, in the context of the lively opposition against the ministers, he claimed that there should be a control of the constitutionality of laws. But neither his denunciations of despotism nor his admiration for the American revolutionaries meant that he took into consideration a democratic or even a

parliamentary regime for France. Nor did he think of revolution as a desirable *choice* to make. He rather both feared the collapse of France and hoped that after a long period of bloodshed his fatherland might regenerate itself, when the seeds of corruption will have been destroyed in fire and tears.

Diderot did not express publicly his hostility towards Maupeou's coup and his approval of the resistance against it. He remained very reserved about French politics, especially compared with the strong opposition to Maupeou that included many writers. It is true that in the 1770s, Diderot had harsh words for Russian despotism, even the "enlightened" government of his main patroness Catherine II, and also that he approved, perhaps with enthusiasm, of the American Revolution. But in his published texts about Catherine like the chapter on Russia in the *History of the Two Indies*, he justified Russian despotism as an unfortunate necessity. His writings defending the rebellion of the American patriots should not be read as an invitation to the French to change their political constitution. There is no evidence that Diderot pleaded in this framework for democracy and even less that he applied these ideas to the French context, which was totally different in his eyes. Justifying the rebellion of the thirteen colonies was rather expected from a French publicist. This meant support for the policy of the French government, a policy whose legitimacy could easily be put into question and that badly needed public support.

The public positions that Diderot maintained also usually fitted to the expectations of the different patrons who supported him during his career, so that it is not always easy to distinguish in his public stances between his personal convictions and necessary concessions to influential individuals. In the early 1750s, Diderot needed to secure his privilege for the *Encyclopédie*, so it is unsurprising that the first volume of this dictionary was not a vector of radical political theory. His support for the *parlementaire* agenda – which was itself not radical as such – was moderate. In the 1760s, he developed an active propaganda on behalf of his mighty patroness, the empress of Russia. His growing distance from physiocracy in the late

1760s is concomitant with his new position as a client of Necker. The patronage given by Aiguillon may explain that Diderot was very reticent in criticising the Maupeou revolution publicly. Diderot had reasons to be very satisfied with his patrons, who made him and his family rich. The story of the last third of his life is that of a steep social ascension. There is no evidence of the supposed strong disappointment in Catherine. Until the end of his life, Diderot seem to have conceived of himself above all as a councillor to monarchs and was obviously not interested to plead for constitutional reforms in pamphlets or newspapers.

To conclude, to which political projects was Diderot's political vision most closely related to in the 1770s and 1780s? Diderot did not envisage a political system in which the nation would be sovereign, the estates abolished, and a parliamentary system established – that is he did not anticipate the French Revolution. His vision was rather akin with that of the “enlightened” finance ministers of Louis XVI's reign: his friend Turgot, his patron Necker and then Calonne or Brienne. All these ministers tried to create a deliberative monarchy in which the elites of the kingdom would advise the king, install checks to despotism, introduce new taxes in order to avoid state bankruptcy, and manage local affairs, but without fundamentally infringing on absolute monarchy (that is the king's uncontrolled freedom of decision within his prerogatives).

Towards the end of his life, Diderot seems to have felt a strong need to justify himself in view of Rousseau's violent criticism of his proximity to leading French courtiers and a notorious despot. Diderot was terrified by the future publication of Rousseau's autobiography, as he had feared Palissot's satire some years before, and in this context he penned his apology for Seneca, that was famously his own too. In contrast, in the 1780s, new *philosophe*-journalists like Jacques-Pierre Brissot would become active and promote much more aggressively the philosophical agenda in the public sphere. Most of them were influenced by Rousseau much more than by Diderot. Rousseau, with his struggle for personal integrity, his criticism of urban and courtly societies, had in the late 1780s become a major point of reference. Voltaire, Raynal,

Helvétius, Mably were other *philosophes* who – for different reasons and in part for different people – raised a kind of awe and almost a cult in the French Revolution. Diderot was much less an admired figure. For the French of the late eighteenth-century, he was someone who had published a major dictionary, but who had otherwise worked for a Russian despot and not put significantly the traditional social and political order into question.

Bibliography

Printed sources

Diderot, Denis, *Correspondance, Œuvres complètes*, vol. 15, ed. Georges Roth and Jean Varloot (Paris: Les Editions de Minuit, 1970).

Diderot, Denis, 'Mélanges philosophiques, historiques, etc. Année 1773 depuis le 15 octobre jusqu'au 3 décembre même année,' in idem, *Œuvres*, vol. 3: *Politique* (Paris: Robert Laffont, 1995).

Diderot, Denis, 'Observations sur l'instruction de S.M.I. aux députés pour la confection des lois,' in idem, *Textes politiques*, ed. Yves Benot (Paris: Éditions sociales, 1960).

Diderot, Denis, *Œuvres politiques: Textes établis avec introductions, bibliographies, notes et relevé de variantes par Paul Vernière* (Paris: Garnier, 1963).

Diderot, Denis, *Essai sur les règnes de Claude et de Néron, et sur les mœurs et les écrits de Sénèque*, 2 vols. (London: s. n., 1782).

Diderot, Denis, 'Autorité politique', in idem, *Encyclopédie ou Dictionnaire raisonné des sciences, des arts et des métiers*, vol. 1, ed. Denis Diderot, (Paris: 1751), URL: <https://artflsrv03.uchicago.edu/philologic4/encyclopedie1117/navigate/1/5134/>.

Diderot, Denis, 'Autorité, pouvoir, puissance, empire', in idem, *Encyclopédie ou Dictionnaire raisonné des sciences, des arts et des métiers*, vol. 1, ed. Denis Diderot, (Paris: 1751), URL: <https://artflsrv03.uchicago.edu/philologic4/encyclopedie1117/navigate/1/5133/>.

Diderot, Denis, 'Cité', in idem, *Encyclopédie ou Dictionnaire raisonné des sciences, des arts et des métiers*, vol. 1, ed. Denis Diderot, (Paris: 1751), URL: <https://artflsrv03.uchicago.edu/philologic4/encyclopedie1117/navigate/3/2165/>.

Diderot, Denis, 'Citoyen', in idem, *Encyclopédie ou Dictionnaire raisonné des sciences, des arts et des métiers*, vol. 1, ed. Denis Diderot, (Paris: 1751), URL: <https://artflsrv03.uchicago.edu/philologic4/encyclopedie1117/navigate/3/2171/>.

Diderot, Denis, 'Droit naturel', in idem, *Encyclopédie ou Dictionnaire raisonné des sciences, des arts et des métiers*, vol. 1, ed. Denis Diderot, (Paris: 1751), URL: <https://artflsrv04.uchicago.edu/philologic4.7/encyclopedie0922/navigate/5/606>.

Jaucourt, Louis de, 'Gouvernement', in Denis Diderot, ed., *Encyclopédie ou Dictionnaire raisonné des sciences, des arts et des métiers*, vol. 1, (Paris: 1751), URL: <https://artflsrv03.uchicago.edu/philologic4/encyclopedie1117/navigate/5/634/>.

Jaucourt, Louis de, 'Liberté politique', in Denis Diderot, ed., *Encyclopédie ou Dictionnaire raisonné des sciences, des arts et des métiers*, vol. 1, (Paris: 1751), URL: <https://artflsrv03.uchicago.edu/philologic4/encyclopedie1117/navigate/5/634/>.

Jaucourt, Louis de, 'Monarchie limitée', in idem, *Encyclopédie ou Dictionnaire raisonné des sciences, des arts et des métiers*, vol. 1, ed. Denis Diderot, (Paris: 1751), URL: <https://artflsrv03.uchicago.edu/philologic4/encyclopedie1117/navigate/5/634/>.

Journal de Trévoux, vol. 1 of 1752, issue 3 (March 1752).

Lex regia, Dig. I,4,1.

Raynal, Guillaume-Thomas, *Histoire philosophique et politique des établissements et du commerce dans les deux Indes*, 10 vols. (Genève: Jean-Léonard Pellet, 1780).

Suárez, Francisco, *Defensio Fidei III. Principatus politicus o la soberania popular*, eds. E. Elorduy and L. Perena (Madrid: Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, 1965).

Turgot, Anne-Robert, *Œuvres posthumes de M. Turgot, ou Mémoire de M. Turgot sur les Administrations provinciales [...]* (Lausanne [Paris?]: s.n., 1787).

Scholarship

Abrosimov, Kirill, *Aufklärung jenseits der Öffentlichkeit: Friedrich Melchior Grimms Correspondance littéraire (1753–1773) zwischen der "République des lettres" und europäischen Fürstenthöfen* (Ostfildern: Thorbecke, 2014).

Borek, Johanna, *Denis Diderot* (Reinbek: Rowohlt, 2000).

Burnand, Léonard, *Les Pamphlets contre Necker: Médias et imaginaire politique au XVIIIe siècle* (Paris: Garnier, 2008).

Chartier, Pierre, 'Fondements anthropologiques de la pensée politique de Diderot au temps de l'Encyclopédie: l'article "Droit naturel"', in *Diderot und die Macht*, ed. Isabelle Deflers (Berlin: Erich Schmidt Verlag, 2015), 157–180.

Coujou, Jean-Paul, 'Political Thought and Legal Theory in Suárez', in ed. Victor Salas, *Companion to Francisco Suárez* (Leiden: Brill, 2014), 29–71.

Crocker, Lester G., 'Diderot as a political philosopher', *Revue internationale de Philosophie* 38 (1984): 120–139.

Curran, Andrew S., *Diderot and the Art of Thinking Freely* (New York: Other Press, 2019).

De Franceschi, Sylvio Hermann, *La crise théologico-politique du premier âge baroque : Antiromanisme doctrinal, pouvoir pastoral et raison du prince ; le Saint-Siège face au prisme français (1606–1627)* (Rome: École française de Rome, 2009).

Deflers, Isabelle, 'Diderots Auseinandersetzung mit dem "aufgeklärten Despotismus" Friedrichs II.', in *Diderot und die Macht*, ed. Isabelle Deflers, (Berlin: Erich Schmidt Verlag, 2015), 61–82.

Deflers, Isabelle, ed., *Diderot und die Macht / Diderot et le pouvoir* (Berlin: Erich Schmidt Verlag, 2015).

Dulac, Georges, 'Les "Observations sur le nakaz": de nouveaux choix éditoriaux', *Diderot Studies* 33 (2013): 107–151.

Echeverria, Durrand, *The Maupeou Revolution: A Study in the History of Libertarianism* (Baton Rouge: Louisiana State University Press, 1985).

Edelstein, Dan, *On the Spirit of Rights* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2019).

Fuchs, Eric, *Le droit de résister: Le protestantisme face au pouvoir* (Genève: Éditions Labor et Fides, 1990).

Furbank, P. N., *Diderot: A critical biography* (London: Secker & Warburg, 1992).

Goggi, Gianluigi, *De l'Encyclopédie à l'éloquence républicaine : Étude sur Diderot et autour de Diderot* (Paris: Honoré Champion, 2013).

Goyard-Fabre, Simone, 'Les idées politiques de *Diderot au temps de l'Encyclopédie*', *Revue internationale de philosophie* 38 (1984): 91–119.

Henshall, Nicholas, *The Myth of Absolutism: Change and Continuity in Early Modern European Monarchy* (London: Longman, 1992).

Heyer, Andreas, *Materialien zum politischen Denken Diderots: Eine Werksmonographie* (Hamburg: Verlag Dr. Kovac, 2004).

Israel, Jonathan, *Democratic Enlightenment. Philosophy, Revolution and Human Rights, 1750–1790* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2011).

Israel, Jonathan, *Enlightenment Contested: Philosophy, Modernity, and the Emancipation of Man, 1670–1752* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2006).

Jouanna, Arlette, *Le Sang des princes: Les ambiguïtés de la légitimité monarchique* (Paris: Gallimard, 2022).

Kerautret, Michel, 'Diderot et la Révolution américaine', in *Diderot und die Macht*, ed. Isabelle Deflers (Berlin: Erich Schmidt Verlag, 2015), 101–19.

Lee, Yong-Mock, 'Diderot et la lutte parlementaire au temps de l'Encyclopédie', *Recherches sur Diderot et sur l'Encyclopédie* 29 (2000), 45–63 (1st part) and 30 (2001), 93–126 (2nd part).

Lilti, Antoine, *L'Héritage des Lumières: Ambivalences de la modernité* (Paris: Seuil, 2019).

Lough, John, *Essays on the Encyclopédie of Diderot and d'Alembert* (London: Oxford University Press, 1968).

Mellet, Paul-Alexis, ed., *Et de sa bouche sortait un glaive: Les monarchomaques au XVIe siècle* (Genève: Droz, 2006).

Mellet, Paul-Alexis, *Les traités monarchomaques: Confusion des temps, résistance armée et monarchie parfaites* (Genève: Droz, 2007).

Ohji, Kenta, 'Raynal, Necker et la Compagnie des Indes: Quelques aspects inconnus de la genèse et de l'évolution de l'Histoire des deux Indes', in *Raynal et ses réseaux*, ed. Gilles Bancarel (Paris: Honoré Champion, 2011), 105–182.

Pečar, Andreas and Tricoire, Damien, 'Diderot the Courtier? Philosophers and the World of the Court in Enlightenment Europe', in *Enlightenment at Court, Patrons, Philosophes and Reformers in Eighteenth-Century Europe*, ed. Thomas Biskup and others (Liverpool: Liverpool University Press), 33–68.

Pečar, Andreas and Tricoire, Damien, *Falsche Freunde: War die Aufklärung wirklich die Geburtsstunde der Moderne?* (Frankfurt am Main: Campus, 2015).

Proust, Jacques, 'Diderot et l'expérience russe: Un exemple de pratique théorique au XVIIIe siècle', *Studies on Voltaire and the Eighteenth Century*, 151–155 (1976), 1777–1800.

Quintili, Paolo, 'Le stoïcisme révolutionnaire de Diderot dans l'Essai sur Sénèque par rapport à la contribution à l'Histoire des deux Indes', *Recherches sur Diderot et sur l'Encyclopédie* 36 (2004): 29–42.

Rebejkow, Jean-Christophe, 'Diderot et les tentatives réformatrices de Catherine II', *Zeitschrift für französische Sprache und Literatur* 126 (2016): 68–104.

Stenger, Gerhardt, *Diderot: Le combattant de la liberté* (Paris: Perrin, 2013).

Strugnell, Anthony, *Diderot's Politics: A Study of the Evolution of Diderot's Political Thought after the Encyclopédie*, (The Hague: Nijhoff, 1972).

Terver, Pierre, *Le dernier prince de Conti à l'Isle-Adam (1776–1789)* (Pontoise: Société historique et archéologique de Pontoise, 1989).

Tricoire, Damien, 'The Fabrication of the philosophe: Catholicisms: Court Culture and the Origins of the Enlightenment Moralism', *Journal for Eighteenth-Century Studies* 51, no. 4 (2018), 453–477.

Tricoire, Damien, 'La Cité de Dieu des patriotes: La pensée théocratique des Lumières et les origines religieuses de la Révolution française', *French Historical Studies* 46, no. 3 (2023).

Tricoire, Damien, 'Raynal's and Diderot's Patriotic History of the Two Indies, or The Problem of Anticolonialism in the Eighteenth Century', *The Eighteenth Century: Theory and Interpretation* 59, no. 4 (2018): 429–448.

Tricoire, Damien, 'Súarez liest Diderot oder Von der Recht-und-Ordnung-Ideologie der Encyclopédie', in *Der lange Weg zur Revolution: Das politische Denken Denis Diderots*, ed. Andreas Heyer, (Baden-Baden: Nomos, 2021), 123–140.

Trousseau, Raymond, *Diderot* (Paris: Éd. Opéra, 2007).

Wilson, Arthur M., *Diderot* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1972).

Wilson, Arthur M., *Diderot* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1957).